

Characterization of Oyster Nut (*Telfairia Pedata*) Stem Particles for Biocomposite Reinforcement: A Comprehensive Study

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Abstract

The global push for sustainable materials in engineering is driven by concerns about environmental impact, resource depletion, and the negative effects of conventional materials. Traditional materials, such as plastics, contribute to pollution and rely on non-renewable resources. As a result, natural fibers are being explored as sustainable alternatives due to their biodegradability, renewability, and lower environmental impact. This study evaluates the potential of Oyster Nut stem particles as reinforcements in biocomposites using DSC-TGA, FT-IR, and XRD analyses. The results indicate that while Oyster Nut demonstrates good thermal stability and contains typical biopolymer components, it is predominantly amorphous with some crystalline regions. These findings suggest significant potential for using Oyster Nut in composite materials, highlighting its promise as a sustainable reinforcement option.

Keywords: Oyster nut (*Telfairia Pedata*), fibrous outer shell, biocomposite, characterization, mechanical properties, thermal properties, morphological analysis

1. Introduction

The global need for sustainable materials in engineering is driven by increasing environmental concerns, resource depletion, and the negative impacts of conventional materials on the planet. Industries are now facing significant pressure to reduce their carbon footprint and adopt eco-friendly alternatives. Traditional engineering materials, such as plastics, metals, and synthetic composites, often rely on non-renewable resources and contribute to pollution throughout their lifecycle, from extraction to disposal. This has led to a surge in demand for sustainable materials that can meet the performance standards required in engineering while minimizing environmental harm. One of the most promising approaches in this transition is the search for natural fibers and fillers as alternatives to synthetic materials. Natural fibers offer several advantages, including biodegradability, renewability, and lower environmental impact compared to petroleum-based materials. These fibers can be sourced from agricultural waste or underutilized crops, further enhancing sustainability. Researchers are actively exploring natural materials like hemp, jute, kenaf, ramie, flax, sisal, coconut, date, pinecone and others for use as reinforcement in composites [1,2].

In this study, we investigate the fundamental characteristics of the stem particles of Oyster nut (*Telfairia pedata*) to evaluate its potential as a reinforcement material in biocomposites. To achieve this, we conducted a series of tests to assess its suitability and explore its possible applications.

Oyster nut is a vine-powerful climbing crop plant that can grow up to 30 meters on tall tree-like supports. It is a *Telfairia* genus from the *Cucurbitaceae* family [3]. It can be found in Tanzania, the Isles of Zanzibar, Pemba and Mozambique and is cultivated in Central, East and Southern Africa. It is commonly found and grown in Rwanda, and Uganda and goes up to Ethiopia and southwards through Tanzania to Zambia, Malawi, Mozambique and South Africa, as seen in Figure 1. In fact, to the authors' knowledge, there are no existing studies on the properties of the oyster nut, to be used in manufacturing biocomposites. Mostly there are studies about it being grown for their seeds obtained from the fruits of this plant, which are enriched with 60% protein and 30% fats [4]. The earliest known study of the Oyster Nut by Poppleton revealed that it is a vine native to East Africa, and grows well at altitudes ranging from 200-300 meters to over 2000 meters.

There are numerous studies on the physical and mechanical properties of various nuts and natural fibers shells. Sampathkumar et al. [6] investigated the thermal stability and flame-retardant properties of composites made from natural fibers (coir, cotton, Palmyra leaf stream, sisal) reinforced with natural rubber, treated with various inorganic flame retardants. Ali [7] characterized *Calotropis procera* fibers through six experimental tests, including SEM, EDX, FT-IR, TGA, DSC, and sound absorption analysis.

Figure 1. Oyster nut and its fruit

2. Material

The oyster nut stems used in this study were obtained from forests in Uganda, ensuring both authenticity and quality. The stems were meticulously cleaned to remove any residual organic material, thoroughly dried to reduce moisture content, and then ground into particles of varying sizes. These particles were subsequently classified based on their size distribution for use in biocomposite fabrication. The samples analyzed were sieved to sizes between 100 μm and 250 μm .

3. Method

Three different tests were conducted on the samples: DSC-TGA analysis, FT-IR analysis, and XRD analysis. These analysis methods and their purposes are briefly explained below.

DSC-TGA (Differential Scanning Calorimetry - Thermogravimetric Analysis) is a combined thermal analysis technique used to study the thermal properties of materials. DSC measures the heat flow associated with phase transitions, such as melting, crystallization, or glass transitions, providing insights into the material's thermal stability and specific heat capacity. TGA, on the other hand, measures the weight loss of a sample as it is heated, which helps in determining the decomposition temperature, moisture content, and thermal degradation patterns. Together, DSC-TGA analysis provides a comprehensive understanding of a material's thermal behavior, crucial for evaluating its suitability for various engineering applications.

FT-IR (Fourier Transform Infrared) analysis is a technique used to identify the chemical bonds and functional groups present in a material by measuring how it absorbs infrared light at different wavelengths. When a material is exposed to infrared radiation, its molecules vibrate at specific frequencies, corresponding to different bond types within the material. The resulting spectrum provides a unique "fingerprint" of the material, revealing information about its molecular structure and composition. FT-IR is particularly useful in characterizing organic materials and polymers, allowing researchers to identify the presence of specific functional groups such as hydroxyl (-OH), carbonyl (C=O), and amine (-NH₂) groups. This analysis is critical in confirming the chemical structure of materials, detecting impurities, and understanding the interactions between different components in a composite. In the context of material development, FT-IR helps ensure that the desired chemical characteristics are present, which is essential for predicting and optimizing material performance in various applications.

XRD (X-ray Diffraction) analysis is a technique used to study the crystalline structure of materials by observing how X-rays are diffracted when they interact with the material's atoms. When X-rays are directed at a crystalline material, they are scattered in specific directions determined by the arrangement of atoms in the crystal lattice. By measuring the angles and intensities of these diffracted beams, XRD can provide detailed information about the crystal structure, including lattice parameters, phase identification, and crystallite size. XRD analysis is essential for identifying the different crystalline phases present in a material, determining its crystallinity, and assessing any structural changes that occur during processing or treatment. This technique is widely used in materials science, chemistry, and

geology to analyze metals, ceramics, polymers, and composites, helping researchers understand the material's properties, predict its behavior, and tailor it for specific applications.

4. Results

4.1. DSC-TGA Analysis

Figure 2. DSC-TGA analysis graph of oyster nut stem

The DSC-TGA graph (Figure 2) for Oyster Nut provides valuable information about the thermal stability and decomposition behavior of the material.

Initial Weight Loss (Below 100°C): There is a slight weight loss below 100°C, which can be attributed to the evaporation of moisture or other volatile compounds present in the material. This is typical for natural fibers, where absorbed water or loosely bound molecules are removed upon heating.

Major Decomposition (Around 250°C - 400°C): The most significant weight loss occurs between approximately 250°C and 400°C. This region corresponds to the thermal decomposition of the organic components of the Oyster Nut shell, such as cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin. The sharp drop in weight indicates the breakdown of these biopolymers into smaller volatile molecules.

Residual Mass (Above 400°C): After 400°C, the rate of weight loss decreases significantly, and the curve flattens out. This suggests that the remaining material is more thermally stable, possibly consisting of carbonaceous residue or ash, which does not decompose further at temperatures up to 600°C.

Interpretation: The TGA analysis indicates that the *Telfairia pedata* shell has good thermal stability up to around 250°C, making it suitable for applications that do not require exposure to high temperatures. The significant degradation between 250°C and 400°C suggests that the material's primary organic components are susceptible to thermal decomposition within this range. The residual mass left after 400°C could be used to determine the ash content or other non-volatile residues, which can be important for understanding the material's behavior in high-temperature applications.

4.2. FT-IR analysis

The FTIR spectrum shown in Figure 3 provides insights into the functional groups present in the Oyster Nut sample. The x-axis represents the wavenumbers (cm^{-1}), indicating the energy of the absorbed infrared light, while the y-axis shows the % transmittance, indicating how much of the infrared light is absorbed by the sample.

O–H Stretching (Broad Peak around 3300-3400 cm^{-1}): The broad peak in the region around 3300-3400 cm^{-1} is indicative of O–H stretching, which is typical of hydroxyl groups (–OH). This suggests the presence of moisture or alcohols, which is common in natural fibers due to their hydrophilic nature.

Figure 3. FTIR analysis graph of oyster nut stem

C–H Stretching (Around 2900 cm^{-1}): The peak observed around 2900 cm^{-1} can be attributed to C–H stretching vibrations, which are characteristic of aliphatic chains (–CH₂, –CH₃). This is consistent with the presence of cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin in the shell.

Carbonyl Group (C=O Stretching at ~1740 cm^{-1}): The peak near 1740 cm^{-1} corresponds to the C=O stretching vibrations, which can be associated with ester, ketone, or aldehyde functional groups. This is often linked to the presence of lignin or hemicellulose in plant-based materials.

C–O Stretching (Around 1000-1300 cm^{-1}): The series of peaks in the region between 1000 and 1300 cm^{-1} indicate C–O stretching vibrations, which are common in carbohydrates such as cellulose. This further confirms the presence of polysaccharides in the shell material.

Fingerprint Region (Below 1500 cm^{-1}): The region below 1500 cm^{-1} is often referred to as the "fingerprint region," where complex vibrations occur. The distinct peaks in this region provide a unique signature that can be used to identify specific components in the sample.

Interpretation: The FTIR spectrum of the *Telfairia pedata* inner shell suggests the presence of typical biopolymer components such as cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin. The broad O–H peak indicates the presence of hydroxyl groups, likely due to water content or alcohols in the material. The presence of C=O and C–O stretching vibrations supports the presence of lignocellulosic materials, which are typical for plant-based shells.

4.3. XRD analysis

The XRD pattern shown in Figure 4 indicates the structural characteristics of the Oyster Nut sample. The graph displays intensity (counts) versus 2Theta (°), which is typical for XRD analysis.

Amorphous Nature: The broad and diffuse peaks, especially between the 20° and 30° range, suggest that the material has a significant amorphous phase. This is typical for natural fibers or plant-based materials where crystalline regions may exist alongside amorphous regions.

Crystallinity Peaks: There are noticeable peaks around 22° and 25° in 2Theta, which could indicate the presence of some crystalline regions within the material. However, these peaks are not very sharp, further supporting that the material is primarily amorphous with some crystalline content.

Intensity: The intensity of the peaks, although present, is relatively low, indicating that the crystalline phases, if present, are not dominant in the sample.

Interpretation: The XRD pattern suggests that the Telfairia pedata inner shell is largely amorphous, with minor crystalline regions. This is consistent with many natural biopolymeric materials, where the amorphous cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin dominate the structure. The presence of broad peaks indicates that while there is some degree of crystallinity, the material's structure is predominantly disordered. This amorphous nature is beneficial in certain composite applications as it can contribute to the material's flexibility and toughness. However, it may also mean that the material may have lower stiffness and strength compared to fully crystalline materials.

Figure 4. XRD analysis graph of oyster nut stem

5. Conclusion

The analysis of Oyster Nut (*Telfairia pedata*) stem particles reveals several key findings about its potential as a biocomposite reinforcement. DSC-TGA analysis demonstrates that the material has good thermal stability up to approximately 250°C, with significant decomposition occurring between 250°C and 400°C. FT-IR analysis confirms the presence of key biopolymer components such as cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin, highlighting its suitability for composite applications. XRD analysis indicates that the material is predominantly amorphous with minor crystalline regions, which could enhance its flexibility and toughness in composite materials. These results suggest that Oyster Nut stems possess promising properties for use in sustainable biocomposites, although their lower crystallinity might affect their stiffness and strength.

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